

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**PRESCRIBING PRACTICES IN PEDIATRICS AND DRUG
UTILIZATION STUDIES PROMOTING PEDIATRIC HEALTH**¹Mudasir Maqbool, ²Dr Sayyab Tariq, ²Dr Sidra Amjad¹Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Kashmir,bhatmudasir.scholar@kashmiruniversity.net²Holy Family Hospital**Abstract:**

Knowledge of drug administration in children and infants lags behind that of adults for many reasons. These include developmental differences that affect the pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic profiles of drugs, ethical and financial reasons, research capabilities, and regulatory guidelines and constraints. Most of the drugs prescribed for children have not been tested in the pediatric population due to the difficulties in carrying out clinical studies in children and ethical issues due to children not being able to make their own decisions to participate in a clinical trial. Epidemiological evaluation of medicine use in elderly is now a highly visible topic, but drug prescribing studies in pediatric patients have been limited. The higher incidence of infections in pediatric population as compared to adults leads to higher prescription of Antimicrobial Drugs (AMDs), at times more than two in single prescription. The use of antibiotics in children has been a major area of concern. . Periodic prescriptions analysis and effective feedback to clinician should be done based on results to ensure rational prescribing and effective health care management, which will ultimately lead to a better child health. In this review article, we will to analyze prescribing practices in pediatrics and drug utilization studies promoting pediatric health.

Key words: *Pediatrics, rationale prescribing, antibiotics, Drug utilization**** Corresponding author:****Mudasir Maqbool,**

Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences,

University of Kashmir,

bhatmudasir.scholar@kashmiruniversity.net

QR code

Please cite this article in press Mudasil Maqbool et al., **Prescribing Practices In Pediatrics and Drug Utilization Studies Promoting Pediatric Health.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(08).

INTRODUCTION:

Knowledge of drug administration in children and infants lags behind that of adults for many reasons. These include developmental differences that affect the pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic profiles of drugs, ethical and financial reasons, research capabilities, and regulatory guidelines and constraints [1]. Irrational drug use, especially antimicrobials in a pediatric population, has become a commonly noted practice. A study in the USA and Canada has shown that 50% and 85% of antibiotics, respectively, were prescribed inappropriately to children [2]. Evidence suggests that medication errors have a higher incidence in children and infants than in adults [3]. The irrational use of drugs is known to an increase in the cost of treatment, incidence of adverse drug reactions. Markets for children's medicines tend to be small and the range of doses used may be wide for any drug formulation because many drugs prescribed widely for infants and children are not available in suitable dosage forms, leading to a lack of attention to pediatric medicines. Most of the drugs prescribed for children have not been tested in the pediatric population due to the difficulties in carrying out clinical studies in children and ethical issues due to children not being able to make their own decisions to participate in a clinical trial. Therefore, many medications have not been approved by the Food and Drug Administration for children [4]. Epidemiological evaluation of medicine use in elderly is now a highly visible topic, but drug prescribing studies in pediatric patients have been limited. The need for the safe and effective drugs for use in sick neonates, infants, children and adolescents requires the establishment of thoughtful drug therapy strategies [5].

Drugs play a key role in protecting, maintaining and restoring health. Prescription writing is a science and an art, as it conveys the message from the prescriber to the patient¹. It is an order for a scientific medication for a person at a particular time. It brings into focus the diagnostic acumen and therapeutic proficiency of the physician with instructions for palliation or restoration of the patient's health [7]. Now-a-days the prescribing pattern is changing and it has become just an indication of medicine with some instructions of doses without considering its rationality [8]. It has been frequently observed that doctors are adopting polypharmacy, promoting unnecessary use of tonics and other drugs under the sales influence of drug companies. Infants and children are among the most vulnerable population groups to contract illnesses [9]. The use of antimicrobial agents, especially antibiotics has become a routine practice for the treatment of pediatric illnesses. There has been an unexplained

world-wide increase in antibiotic use the last decades. Overuse and misuse of antibiotics lead to unnecessary side effects, costs and emergence of antibiotic resistant bacteria [10-13]. Although the antimicrobial agents are effective and play an important role in the management of infectious diseases, they have serious consequences. The worldwide multi-drug resistant microorganisms were identified and were associated with the widespread use of antimicrobial agents in both inpatients and outpatients. For example, many studies have shown that there is an emergence of resistant strains of *Streptococcus pneumoniae* to antimicrobial agents and these strains are rapidly increasing [14]. The emergence of multi-drug resistant microorganisms is expected to lead to more serious infections than what we have initially encountered. Another serious problem associated with the irrational use of antimicrobials, especially among pediatrics, is the ability of strong antibiotics to disturb the colonization of gastro-intestinal micro flora which may induce serious clinical symptoms like pseudo membranous colitis and toxic megacolon [15]. In order to have the concept of essential drug program to promote rational drug use, WHO published its report on selection of essential drugs in 1977. Further to promote the rational use of drugs, the concept of drug utilization came into picture. Drug utilization review is the process by which the quality of drug prescribing is measured by organizing important predetermined criteria [16]. DURs form part of the quality assurance (QA) programmes within hospitals and are designed to monitor the use of prescription medicines [17].

Drug utilization studies in pediatric settings

One of the important objectives of a drug utilization study is to find out rationality in drug use. Drug use indicators developed by WHO are highly standardized and are being field tested from time to time. One such initial study was done by international network for the rational use of drugs in collaboration with the WHO action program on essential drugs to develop and field test a set of basic drug use indicators. The study was carried out in 12 developing countries. The results showed that average number of drugs per encounter was high in Indonesia and Nigeria (3.3 & 3.8); prescription of antibiotics were high in Uganda and Sudan (56% & 63%); 94% of drugs were prescribed by generic name in Zimbabwe, whereas only 375 in Ecuador [18]. Similar studies using WHO recommended indicator has been carried out in different countries like Spain, Sweden, Italy, Tanzania, Nigeria etc. to understand drug use pattern in pediatric out patients [19-24]. In India also drug utilization studies have been carried out in order to provide insight into the drug

use patterns and prescribing practices. While there are several studies in adults [25-27], few studies has

been carried out in pediatric setting. Such studies on pediatric population are compared in table.

Comparison of DUR studies in INDIA [28-31]

	Mirza et al (2000)	Mathur et al (2004)		Karande et al (2005)	Dimri et al(2006)
Indicators	Ped.OPD	Ped. Govt.*	Ped. Sat.#	Ped. OPD	Ped. OPD
Number of prescriptions	606	63	56	500	254
Average no of drugs/ prescription	3.72	4.02	4.57	2.9	2.31
% encounter with an antibiotic prescribed		33.3%	39.2%	39.6%	29.1%
% encounter with an injection prescribed		-	-	0.2%	1.18%
% drug prescribed with generic names	30.7%	-	-	73.4%	5.8%
% drugs prescribed from EDL	77.61%	-	-	90.3%	45%

* Ped. Govt = Pediatrics, Government Hospital; # Ped. Sat. = Pediatrics, Satellite Hospital

Use of Antimicrobial drugs in hospitalized children.

The higher incidence of infections in pediatric population as compared to adults leads to higher prescription of Antimicrobial Drugs (AMDs), at times more than two in single prescription. The use of antibiotics in children has been a major area of concern. In a prospective study involving 2171 pediatric Bangladeshi in patients, it was found that the most commonly prescribed antimicrobials in children for infections (like bronchopneumonia and diarrhea) were ampicillin, gentamicin, amoxicillin, cloxacillin and ceftriaxone. The results of this study showed that 56.1% of the admitted children received two or more antimicrobials in combinations for treatment [32]. The same study also revealed that there was a high level of inappropriate antimicrobial treatment for the most common infectious disease and suggested the need for intervention to improve

antimicrobial use in hospitals. Results of various studies have shown that antibiotics were prescribed to 30 - 70% of the pediatric patients with upper respiratory tract infection, to 30 - 76% patients with bronchitis, 44.1% with tonsillitis, 10 - 44% with common cold and 76% patients with acute pharyngitis [33-37]. Though decreased use of antibiotic for respiratory tract infection has been reported in many studies but use of inappropriate antibiotic is still common and use has not been reduced for all antibiotics and all children [38-41]. For example a study done by Arch et al showed that there was decline in use of antibiotics for URI and bronchitis but there was also proportional increase in prescribing of broad spectrum antibiotics [42]. In another two studies also it was reported that there was increased use of broad spectrum macrolides among preschool children [43-44]. The results of a study carried out in Madagascar on evaluation of the

antibiotics' usage in pediatric in-patients showed that three antibiotic families' co-trimoxazole, penicillins derivatives and amino glycosides were frequently used. The result showed that antibiotic prescriptions were irrational; and, the probable reason was insufficiency of biological labs and expensive costs of laboratory tests [45]. In yet another retrospective study on antimicrobial prescribing patterns in Trinidad involving a total of 527 cases, it was found that 44% of patients had received one or more antibiotics and pediatric patients received 70.8% of antibiotics. The most frequently prescribed antibiotics to children were ampicillin, chloramphenicol and gentamicin. The reason for overuse of antibiotics was poor communication and lack of confidence in laboratory technician expertise [46]. In a study on use of antimicrobial agents for treating community acquired lower respiratory tract infections, the prescriptions of a total of 613 children (age 2-14 years) hospitalized for acute bronchitis or pneumonia were analyzed, it was found that 92.1% children received AMD [47]. Likewise, another study done in Italy on clinical and economic outcomes of pneumonia in children, 99 inpatients of pediatric hospital receiving antibiotic treatment were enrolled. A parenteral antibiotic therapy was administered in 64.6% of cases whereas 35.4% received oral antibiotic therapy; the most frequently prescribed parenteral antibiotic was ceftriaxone and for oral antibiotic therapy cefprozil. The study concluded that hospital management of pediatric pneumonia was influenced by the early discharge policy than by clinical variables without under-cure [48].

In a prospective survey of antibiotic utilization in pediatric hospitalized patients in Switzerland it was found that in total 125 out of 349 patients were prescribed with 246 antibiotics out of which medical ward pediatric patients received 42% of antibiotics compared with surgical ward pediatric patients (31%). It was found in this study that empirical prescription was more frequent than therapeutic or prophylactic prescription. The rate of inappropriate prescription was similar in both wards in which higher inappropriate prescription rates were noted for macrolides, co-trimoxazole and betalactams [49]. A study done in Ethiopia on prescribing pattern of AMDs on 407 patients found that 82% antibiotics were prescribed in pediatric ward and the most frequently prescribed antibiotic was penicillin, chloramphenicol and ampicillin. It was concluded that there was inappropriate use of antibacterial and a need to develop a policy on hospital antibacterial use was felt [50]. Prescribing by generic name has been declining and should be encouraged. This was reported by a study carried out in the pediatric

patients at Nepal which aimed to assess the drug prescribing patterns and average cost of the drugs. In a sample of 356 patients, the average number of drugs prescribed per admission was 4.5; and 48.9% drugs were administered by the parenteral route. Antibiotics were prescribed in 69.9% cases and *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Acinetobacter species* were the common microorganisms isolated. The average (\pm SD) cost of drugs per admission was 5.4 (\pm 1.6) US dollars [51]. The results from a pediatric hospital in Kathmandu on prescribing patterns of antibiotics revealed that a high percentage of patients (93%) were prescribed at least one antibiotic among the 121 pediatric patients analyzed. Benzyl penicillin and gentamicin/cefotaxim were found to be mostly used combination antibiotics in case of pneumonia which was the most prevalent disease. In this study, 75% of antibiotics were given by injection. The average number of antibiotic per patient was 2.41 ± 1.02 [52].

A study conducted on antibiotic utilization for hospitalized pediatric patients in Netherlands revealed that antibiotics were prescribed at least once for 36% of hospitalized children although only 12.3% of the patients receiving antibiotics had proven bacterial infection. It was also concluded that a high percentage of all hospitalized children receive antibiotics whereas in most cases they are started on an empirical basis, without proof of a bacterial infection [53].

Education and experience of physician, parental expectations and economic pressure has been suggested as possible reasons for over prescribing of antibiotics in children [55]. In a questionnaire study it was reported that patients presenting with acute lower respiratory tract infections symptoms often believe that infection is the problem and antibiotic is the answer and patient pressure most commonly influenced the decision to prescribe even when doctor thought antibiotic were not indicated [56]. Further it was demonstrated in a study that children with physician -parents were least likely to receive potentially inappropriate antibiotic preparations suggesting the role of parental education. However parental education alone is not sufficient to effect change; factors like ready access to care on an urgent basis, better communication between treating physician and physician - patient relationships when the patient is a physician, may play a role in reducing inappropriate use of antibiotics [57].

CONCLUSION:

Infant health is as important as elderly health. A wide gap is found about the literature related to pediatric

health. There is still scope of improvement in various areas like dosage calculation, proper documentation, prescribing drugs by generic name and from WHO-EML for children as far as possible. Development and implementation of Standard Treatment Guidelines (STGs) based on essential drug concept and promoting rational drug therapy will lead to more and more rational prescribing in pediatrics. Periodic prescriptions analysis and effective feedback to clinician should be done based on results to ensure rational prescribing and effective health care management, which will ultimately lead to a better child health.

REFERENCES:

1. Clavenna A, Berti A, Gualandi L, Rossi E, De Rosa M, Bonati M. Drug utilisation profile in the Italian pediatric population. *Eur J Pediatr* 2009;168:173-80.
2. Lusini G, Lapi F, Sara B, Vannacci A, Mugelli A, Kragstrup J, et al. Antibiotic prescribing in pediatric populations: A comparison between Viareggio, Italy and Funen, Denmark. *Eur J Public Health* 2009;19:434-8.
3. Di Paolo E, Gehri M, Ouedraogo-Ruchet L, Sibailly G, Lutz N, Pannatier A. Outpatient prescriptions practice and writing quality in a pediatric university hospital. *Swiss Med Wkly* 2012;142:w13564.
4. You ML, Chun Y, Yung TK, Man YH, Hsiang YC. Outcomes of pharmacy interventions on pediatric medication prescribing patterns in Taiwan. *Int J Clin Exp Med*. 2010;2:173-80.
5. Kliegman, Behrman, Jenson, Stanton. Nelson Text book of Pediatrics. 18th Edition. Philadelphia : Elsevier Health Sciences;2007; 331-332. Kishore J. National Health Programs of India. 6th ed. New Delhi: Century Publications; 2006:370.
6. Kishore J. National Health Programs of India. 6th ed. New Delhi: Century Publications; 2006:370
7. Benet LZ. Principles of prescription order writing and patients compliance instructions. In: Goodman AG, Rall TW, Nies AS, Taylor P, (eds). Goodman and Gilman's The pharmacological basis of therapeutics. 8th ed. New York: Pergamon Press Inc. 1991:1640.
8. Gaud RS, Jain DK, Kaskhedikar SG, Chaturvedi SC. Critical evaluation of present prescribing pattern. *Indian J Hosp Pharm* 1989;26:70-72.
9. Kaushal R, Jaggi T, Walsh K, Fortescue EB, Bates DW. Pediatric medication errors: what do we know? what gaps remain? *Ambulatory Pediatrics* 2004;4:73-81
10. Sanz EJ, Bergman U, Dahlstorm M. Paediatric drug prescribing. *Eur J clin pharmacol* 1989;37(1):65-68
11. Cunin CM. Resistance to antimicrobial drugs- a worldwide calamity. *Ann Int Med* 1993;118:557-61.
12. Rivero M, Padilla B, Garcia-Lechuz J, Menarguez MC, Rodriguez-Creixems M, Bouza E. Use and misuse of antimicrobial agents in a general hospital in the AIDS era. *J Hosp Infect* 2000;46:230-5.
13. Van Houten MA, Laseur M, Kimpen JLL. Shift in antibiotic prescribing pattern in relation to antibiotic expenditures in paediatrics. *Eur J Pediatr* 1998;157:479-81
14. Greenberg D, Dagon R, Muallem M, Porat N. Antibiotic-resistant invasive pediatric streptococcus pneumoniae clones in Israel. *J Clin Microbiol* 2003;41(12):5541-5.
15. Arvola T, Laiho K, Torkkeli S, Mykkanen H, Salminen S, Maunula L, Isolauri E. Prophylactic Lactobacillus GG reduces antibiotic-associated diarrhea in children with respiratory infections: a randomized study. *Pediatrics*, 104(5), Nov (1999), e64-6.
16. Thaakur SR, Deepthi V, Sowjanya N, Maheswari E, Saraswathy GR. Study of utilization pattern of antimicrobials in paediatric outpatients. *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.* 2007 Apr;6(2):104-7.
17. Lisa KP, Susan ET. Drug utilization review across jurisdictions – a reality or still a distant dream. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol* 2006 Jan; 62: 97-06
18. Hogerzeil HV, Bimo, Ross-Degnan D, Lanig RO, Adjei D, Santoso B, et al. Field test for rational drug use in twelve developing countries. *Lancet*. 1993;342(8884):1408-10.
19. Sanz EJ, Bergman U, Dahlstrom M. Paediatric drug prescribing. A comparison of Tenerife (Canary Islands, Spain) and Sweden. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol*. 1989;31(1):65-8.
20. Cazzato T, Pandolfini C, Campi R, Bonati M. Drug prescribing in out-patient children in Southern Italy. *European Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*. 2001;57(8):611-6.
21. Ootom S, Batieha A, Hadidi H, Hasan M, Al-Saudi K. Evaluation of drug use in Jordan using WHO prescribing indicators. *East Mediterrian Health Journal*. 2002;8(4-5):537-43.
22. Sanz E, Hernández MA, Ratchina S, Stratchounsky L, Peiré MA, Lapeyre-Mestre M, et al. Drug utilisation in outpatient children. A comparison among Tenerife, Valencia, and Barcelona (Spain), Toulouse (France), Sofia (Bulgaria), Bratislava (Slovakia) and Smolensk (Russia) *European Journal of Clinical*

- Pharmacology. 2004;60(2):127-34.
23. Nsimba SE. Assessing prescribing and patient care indicators for children under five years old with malaria and other disease conditions in public primary health care facilities. *Southeast Asian J Trop Med Public Health*. 2006;37(1):206-14.
 24. Nwolisa CE, Erinaughu EU, Ofoleta SI. Prescribing practices of doctors attending to under fives in a children's outpatient clinic in Owerri, Nigeria. *J Trop Pediatr*. 2006;52(3):197-200.
 25. Biswas NR, Biswas RS, Pal PS, Jain SK, Malhotra SP, Gupta A, et al. Patterns of prescriptions and drug use in two tertiary hospitals in Delhi. *Indian J Physiol Pharmacol*. 2000;44(1):109-12.
 26. Hazra A, Tripathi SK, Alam MS. Prescribing and dispensing activities at the health facilities of a non-governmental organization. *The National Medical Journal of India*. 2000;13(4):177-82.
 27. Maini R, Verma KK, Biswas NR, Agrawal SS. Drug utilization study in dermatology in a tertiary hospital in Delhi. *Indian J Physiol Pharmacol*. 2002;46(1):107-10.
 28. Mathur M, Dandiya PC. Prescribing pattern for outpatients in government hospitals in Jaipur. *Indian J Pharmacol*. 2004;36(6):383-4.
 29. Karande S, Sankhe P, Kulkarni M. Patterns of prescription and drug dispensing. *Indian J Pediatr*. 2005;72:117-21.
 30. Nazima Y, Mirza, Sagun Desai, Barna Ganguly. Prescribing pattern in a pediatric out-patient department in Gujarat. *Bangladesh J Pharmacol* 2009;4:39-42
 31. S Dimri, P Tiwari, S Basu, VR Parmar. Drug use pattern in children at a teaching hospital. *Indian Pediatrics* 2009 Feb 17;46:165-7.
 32. Akter FU, Heller D, Smith A, et al. Antimicrobial use in paediatric wards of teaching hospitals in Bangladesh. *Mymensingh Medical J* 2004; 13:63-6.
 33. Nyquist A, Gonzales R, Steiner J, Sande MA. Antibiotic prescribing for children with colds, upper respiratory tract infections, and bronchitis. *Journal of American Medical Association*. 1998;279(11):875-7.
 34. Wang EEL, Thomas TR, Kellner JD, Conly JM. Antibiotic prescribing for Canadian preschool children: evidence of overprescribing for viral respiratory infections. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 1999;29:155-60.
 35. Gonzales R, Malone DC, Maselli JH, Sande MA. Excessive antibiotic use for acute respiratory infections in the United States. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 2001;33:757-62.
 36. Balabanova Y, Fedorin I, Kuznetsov S, Graham C, Ruddy M, Atun R, et al. Antimicrobial prescribing patterns for respiratory diseases including tuberculosis in Russia: a possible role in drug resistance? *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*. 2004;54:673-9.
 37. Andre M, Odenholt I, Schwan A, Axelsson I, Eriksson M, Hoffman M, et al. Upper respiratory tract infections in general practice: diagnosis, antibiotic prescribing, duration of symptoms and use of diagnostic tests. *Scandinavian Journal of Infectious Diseases*. 2002;34(12):880-6.
 38. McCaig LF, Besser RE, Hughes JM. Trends in antimicrobial prescribing rates for children and adolescents. *Journal of American Medical Association*. 2002;287(23):3096-102.
 39. Nash DR, Harman J, Wald ER, Kelleher KJ. Antibiotic prescribing by primary care physicians for children with upper respiratory tract infections *Archives of Pediatrics and Adolescent medicine*. 2002;156:1114-9.
 40. Finkelstein JA, Stille C, Nordin J, Davis R, Raebel MA, Roblin D, et al. Reduction in antibiotic use among US children, 1996-2000. *Pediatrics*. 2003;112:620-7.
 41. Marra F, Patrick DM, Chong M, Bowie WR. Antibiotic use among children in British Columbia, Canada. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*. 2006;58(4):830-9.
 42. Mainous AG, Hueston WJ, Davis MP, Pearson WS. Trends in antimicrobial prescribing for bronchitis and upper respiratory infections among adults and children. *American Journal of Public Health*. 2003;93(11):1910-4.
 43. Kozyrskyj AL, Carrie AG, Mazowita GB, Lix LM, Klassen TP, Law BJ. Decrease in antibiotic use among children in the 1990s: not all antibiotics, not all children. *CMAJ* 2004;171(2):133-8.
 44. Otter HBM, Wouden JCvd, Schellevis FG, Suijlekom-Smit LWAv, Koes BW. Trends in prescribing antibiotics for children in Dutch general practice. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*. 2004;53:361-6.
 45. Rasamoelisoa JM, Tovone XG, Andriamady C, et al. Evaluation of the use of antibiotics in the hospital paediatric milieu. *Arch Inst Pasteur Madagascar* 1999; 65:124-6
 46. Orrett FA. Antimicrobial prescribing patterns at a rural hospital in Trinidad: evidence for intervention measures. [Afr J Med Med Sci](#). 2001 Sep;30(3):161-4
 47. Esposito S, Blasi F, Allegra L. et al Use of antimicrobial agents for community-acquired lower respiratory tract infections in hospitalised children. *Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis* 2001.

- 20(9):647–50
48. [Di Ciommo V](#), [Russo P](#), [Attanasio E](#), [Di Liso G](#), [Graziani C](#), [Caprino L](#). Clinical and economic outcomes of pneumonia in children: a longitudinal observational study in an Italian paediatric hospital. [J Eval Clin Pract](#). 2002 Aug;8(3):341-8.
 49. Potocki M, Goette J, Szucs TD, Nadal D. Prospective survey of antibiotic utilization in pediatric hospitalized patients to identify targets for improvement of prescription. *Infection*. 2003;31(6):398-403.
 50. [Aseffa A](#), [Desta Z](#), [Tadesse I](#). Prescribing pattern of antibacterial drugs in a teaching hospital in Gondar, Ethiopia. [East Afr Med J](#). 1995 Jan;72(1):56-9
 51. Shankar PR, Partha P, Shenoy NK, et al. Prescribing patterns of antibiotics and sensitivity patterns of common microorganisms in the Internal Medicine ward of a teaching hospital in Western Nepal: a prospective study. *Ann Clin Microbiol Antimicrob* 2003;2:7.
 52. Palikhe N. Prescribing pattern of antibiotics in paediatric hospitals in Kathmandu valley. *Kathmandu Univ Med J* 2004;2:6-12.
 53. Vanhouten MA, Luinge K, Laseur M, Kimpen JL. Antibiotic utilization for hospitalized paediatric patients. *Int J Antimicrob Agents* 1998; 10:161-4
 54. [Dharnidharka VR](#), [Kandoth P](#). Paediatric inpatient morbidity patterns and drug usage in a teaching hospital serving an underdeveloped area. [Indian J Public Health](#). 1999 Apr-Jun;43(2):64-6
 55. Schwartz B, Mainous AG, Marcy SM. Why do physicians prescribe antibiotics for children with upper respiratory tract infections. *Journal of American Medical Association*. 1998;279(11):881-2.
 56. Macfarlane J, Holmes W, Macfarlane R, Britten N. Influence of patient's expectations on antibiotic management of acute lower respiratory tract illness in general practice: questionnaire study. *British Medical Journal*. 1997;315:1211-4.
 57. Huang N, Morlock L, Lee C, Chen L, Chou Y. Antibiotic prescribing for children with nasopharyngitis (common cold), upper respiratory infections, and bronchitis who have health professional parents. *Pediatrics* 2005; 116(4):826-32.